

Advancing Urban Flood Resilience with Integrated Hydrologic– Hydraulic Models and Green Stormwater Infrastructure

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Abstract

Climate change is intensifying extreme rainfall events, increasing urban flood risks, particularly in rapidly urbanizing countries like Nepal. In the Kathmandu Valley, monsoon-induced inundation has become more frequent, causing major socio-economic impacts. This study assesses future flood hazards in the lower Manohara River Basin, a key tributary of the Bagmati River system. The HEC-HMS hydrologic model was coupled with the two-dimensional HEC-RAS hydraulic model to simulate upstream runoff and downstream inundation. High-resolution precipitation data from the Non-Hydrostatic Regional Climate Model (NHRCM) under the SSP5-8.5 scenario were used to estimate flood hazards for return periods of 5–100 years under historical (1981–2000) and future (2080–2099) conditions. Model calibration against the August 9-10, 2022 flood event showed good performance. Results indicate that increasing recurrence intervals and climate change both amplify flood depth and inundation extent, shifting low-risk areas into medium- and high-risk zones.

To address these risks, the study highlights the importance of integrating Green Stormwater Infrastructure strategies into urban planning. Approaches such as permeable pavements, infiltration trenches, basins, and stormwater reuse systems can reduce runoff, improve water quality, and enhance urban resilience. Together, advanced flood modeling and sustainable stormwater management provide pathways to mitigate future flood impacts and support resilient urban development in the Kathmandu Valley.

Keywords: *Bagmati river system, climate change, flood risk, urban resilience*